

Supplemental data. Analyses

Supplementary Figure 1. Proto-genes emergence

Supplementary Figure 2. Motifs in de novo genes with 95% similarity PSSM

We calculated the presence of motifs upstream de novo genes and in other test regions, based on « distance weight matrix ». We used a threshold of similarity to the matrix of 0.8, and 0.95 respectively. Both thresholds produced the same trends. A low threshold allows my program to consider some sequences as being motifs if they diverge from the referent motif to 80 %. The highest is the threshold found, the most similar is the motif to the referent motif sequence.

We wondered if the average threshold of similarity of the motifs found upstream de novo genes increased with the age, which could indicate that the motifs are under selection. We found no increase with age.

Supplementary Figure 3. Distribution of motifs from MotifsAllUpstream

Distribution of motifs from MotifsAllUpstream. Mean value for dataset “MotifAllUpstream”: 9.9309, mean value for dataset “human established genes”: 9.059918, mean value for dataset “ncRNA”: 10.73909, mean value for dataset “pseudogenes”: 10.86547, mean value for dataset “non coding region”: 10.62513, mean value for dataset “introns”: 10.83398.

Statistical Values between the datasets: student test were applied to compare the distributions.

```
t.test(DeNovoGene, Gene) ## p-value: 1.036e-14 :difference
t.test(DeNovoGene, ncRNA) ## p-value: 1.024e-10 :difference
t.test(DeNovoGene, pseudogene) ## p-value: 6.383e-11 :difference
t.test(DeNovoGene, non_coding_region) ## p-value: 2.445e-08 :difference
t.test(DeNovoGene, intron) ## p-value: 7.968e-13 :difference
t.test(Gene, DeNovoGene) ## p-value: 1.036e-14 :difference
t.test(Gene, ncRNA) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
t.test(Gene, pseudogene) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
t.test(Gene, non_coding_region) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
t.test(Gene, intron) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
```

Supplementary figure 4 Distribution of motifs from "MotifsCore" database

Mean value of motifs from “MotifsCore” in the 6 lists of the dataset: mean value for dataset “De novo genes”: 3.216596, mean value for dataset “human established genes”: 3.83997, mean value for dataset “ncRNA”: 3.044328, mean value for dataset “pseudogenes”: 2.993224, mean value for dataset “non coding region”: 2.742825, mean value for dataset “introns”: 2.726876

Statistical Values between the datasets: student test were applied to compare the distributions.

```
t.test(DeNovoGene, Gene) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
t.test(DeNovoGene, ncRNA) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
t.test(DeNovoGene, pseudogene) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
t.test(DeNovoGene, non_coding_region) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
t.test(DeNovoGene, intron) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
t.test(Gene, DeNovoGene) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
t.test(Gene, ncRNA) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
t.test(Gene, pseudogene) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
t.test(Gene, non_coding_region) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
t.test(Gene, intron) ## p-value: 2.2e-16 :difference
```

Supplemental Table1. Functions of the 50 motifs most found upstream intergenic de novo genes

As we demonstrated in the main text, intergenic de novo genes are more often found associated with enhancer motifs. We searched for enhancer motifs that were found associated most often to intergenic de novo genes, and found even more in these de novo genes than in non-coding regions. From these motifs, I investigated the function of the 50 more found, and my results are presented below.

Almost all the genes studied (48/50) are associated to a homeobox, and involved in developmental functions. As of yet, I am unsure what to conclude from such unexpected results.

All of the functions were established with geneCard.

Motif	Function
HOXA4	Homeobox Genes. Regulated during embryonic development
HOXC8	Homeobox Genes. Regulated during embryonic development
HOXB6	Homeobox Genes. Regulated during embryonic development
HOXB3	Homeobox Genes. Regulated during embryonic development
HOXC4	Homeobox Genes. Regulated during embryonic development
HOXD4	Homeobox Genes. Regulated during embryonic development
HOXA7	Homeobox Genes. Regulated during embryonic development
HOXB4	Homeobox Genes. Regulated during embryonic development
HOXA1	Homeobox Genes. Regulated during embryonic development
FOXC1	Regulation of embryonic development
FOXP3	Regulation of embryonic development
FOXL1	Regulation of embryonic development
Foxd3	Regulation of embryonic development
FOXC2	Regulation of embryonic development
GSX1	Homeobox
GSX2	Homeobox
Dlx4	Homeobox
DLX6	Homeobox

Dlx3	Homeobox
Dlx1	Homeobox
Dlx2	Homeobox
LHX1	Homeobox development of the renal and urogenital systems
Lhx4	Homeobox development of the renal and urogenital systems
Lhx8	Homeobox development of the renal and urogenital systems
BARHL2	Homeobox
BARHL1	Homeobox
BARX2	Homeobox
NKX6-2	Homeobox Transcription factor with repressor activity involved in the regulation of axon-glia interactions at myelin paranodes in oligodendrocytes
NKX6-1	Homeobox
VAX1	Ventral Anterior Homeobox 1
VAX2	Ventral Anterior Homeobox 2
SOX15	(SRY-related HMG-box) family of transcription factors involved in the regulation of embryonic development and in the determination of the cell fate
Sox3	
DRGX	Paired-Like Homeodomain Transcription Factor. Transcription factor required for the formation of correct projections from nociceptive sensory neurons to the dorsal horn of the spinal cord and normal perception of pain
MIXL1	Mix Paired-Like Homeobox transcription factors that regulate cell fate during development
Arid3a	embryogenesis
NOTO	Notochord Homeobox. notochord development
EVX2	Homeobox Even-Skipped Homolog Protein 2
ESX1	Homeobox Even-Skipped Homolog Protein 2
EVX1	Homeobox Even-Skipped Homolog Protein 2
UNCX	Truncated UNCX Homeobox Protein somitogenesis and neurogenesis and is required for the maintenance and differentiation of specific elements of the axial skeleton
MNX1	Motor Neuron And Pancreas Homeobox 1
Shox2	Paired-Related Homeobox Protein SHOT. This

	gene is a member of the homeobox family of genes that encode proteins containing a 60-amino acid residue motif that represents a DNA binding domain
EN1	Homeobox Protein Engrailed-1. Control of pattern formation during development of the central nervous system
RAX2	Retina And Anterior Neural Fold Homeobox 2, plays a role in eye development
ISX	Intestine Specific Homeobox. Involved in early embryonic development
LIN54	Regulator of cell cycle genes
BSX	Brain-Specific Homeobox Protein Homolog
PRRX1	Paired Mesoderm Homeobox Protein 1. Homeobox proteins localized to the nucleus. The protein functions as a transcription co-activator, enhancing the DNA-binding activity of serum response factor, a protein required for the induction of genes by growth and differentiation factors
ZNF384	Zinc Finger Protein

Supplementary Figure 5 Sizes of 5'UTRs

Supplementary Figure 6. Motifs in UTRs regions

We investigated the motifs that I was able to find in the UTRs regions. To do so, we used a database called ATRACT, which is a database of RNA binding proteins and associated motifs. The motifs found in this database are all specific to RNA, and we investigated them in 5'UTRs of human *de novo* and established genes. Surprisingly, we found more of these motifs in intergenic and intronic *de novo* genes than in exonic ones.

Supplementary Figure 7 Number of human established genes and de novo genes with at least one domain

Supplementary Figure 8 Number of de novo genes containing one domain, according to their age and their genomic position

Supplementary Figure 9 Domains' functions of most enriched domains found in de novo genes

Supplemental Table 2. Student statistical test. HCA domains compared by age and genomic position.

Age class	Genomic position 1	Genomic position 2	p-value
I0	"exonic"	"intronic"	2.454e-07
I0	"exonic"	"intergenic"	9.781e-08
I0	"intronic"	"intergenic"	0.02958
I1	"exonic"	"intronic"	0.001492
I1	"exonic"	"intergenic"	0.000994
I1	"intronic"	"intergenic"	0.38
I2	"exonic"	"intronic"	0.005467
I2	"exonic"	"intergenic"	0.0003656
I2	"intronic"	"intergenic"	0.0004015
I3	"exonic"	"intronic"	1.27e-06
I3	"exonic"	"intergenic"	1.547e-07
I3	"intronic"	"intergenic"	0.0356
I4	"exonic"	"intronic"	2.2e-16
I4	"exonic"	"intergenic"	2.2e-16
I4	"intronic"	"intergenic"	2.475e-07

Supplementary Figure 10 PTI values in de novo genes, according to the age and the genomic position

Following the paper by Suenaga and al., 2021, we calculated the PTI values for the de novo genes, according to their age and genomic positions. In each transcript, we calculated the size of the longest coding sequence, and divided it by the sum of all the putative coding sequences that were found in the transcript, in the 3 frames of the correct direction of the transcription. In their paper, the authors found that the human genes have an average PTI value of 0.55, while the non-coding RNA have an average PTI of 0.15. In our paper, I considered the size of the coding sequence of the de novo gene and retrieved the size of all the coding sequences found in the transcript in the forward or reverse direction corresponding to the transcript. Interestingly, the PTI values of the intergenic and intronic de novo genes are rather high, between 0.45 and 0.70 according to the age. We see these values decreasing with age, but even at their lower level they remain significantly higher than what was found for non-coding RNA.

Contrarily, the PTI values of the exonic de novo genes are a bit lower than the average PTI values of existing human genes. We would hypothesis that this is because the ORFs of the exonic de novo genes might not be the longest ORFs of these transcripts, as they overlap with already existing ORFs that may be longer. Moreover, exonic de novo ORFs come from longer transcripts than intronic and intergenic de novo ORFs. Indeed, the longer the transcript, the more ORFs it is able to contain.

However, our methodology is partly biased compared to the paper of Suenaga and al., 2021, for two reasons.

First, Suenaga et al only used genes and non-coding RNA whose sequences were longer than 200bp. We used all the de novo genes that were available, some being quite small.

Secondly, they calculated the ORFs of a transcript without any limit of size. In our case, we used the dataset of Dowling et al., 2020, who searched all the ORFs of his transcripts, and for each transcript having no BLAST hit, took the longest as being the de novo ORFs. However, when Dowling et al., 2020, searched for ORFs in transcripts, he put a size limit of 30 nucleotides. In my own calculations, all of the ORFs smaller than this size are not taken into account. Indeed, our PTI values are overestimated.

Supplemental Table3. Number of proto-genes per age and genomic positions

	"exonic"	"intronic"	"intergenic"
I0	63	2363	1960
I1	39	536	455
I2	50	611	592
I3	86	714	723
I4	451	2106	2090
I5	12893	814	1004

Supplemental Table4. Average size of ORFs according to the age and the genomic positions

	"exonic"	"intronic"	"intergenic"
I0	379	219	205
I1	452	246	237
I2	444	269	244
I3	440	272	240
I4	521	295	257
I5	1935	510	556

Supplemental Table 5. Average ORFs' GC content (in percentage) according to the age and the genomic positions

	"exonic"	"intronic"	"intergenic"
I0	60.55	49.55	49.32
I1	62.50	51.01	50.79
I2	60.92	50.98	50.27
I3	60.99	51.10	49.83
I4	60.18	50.94	50.10
I5	55.36	49.98	50.02

Supplementary Figure 11. Energy distribution of 5'UTRs from sizes ranging from 0 to 250 pb.

Supplementary Figure 12. Number of HCA clusters according to the ORF's size of the proto-genes.

Supplementary Figure 13. Number of HCA clusters according to the GC content of proto-genes' ORFs.

